

Bromination by N-Bromosaccharin of *p*-Substituted Anisoles in 50% Aqueous Acetic Acid

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N-BROMOSACCHARIN (NBSA) is sometimes used^{1,2} as a brominating agent for aromatic compounds. It is superior to N-bromosuccinimide (NBS) because of its greater stability, stronger electrophilic nature and free radical-free bromination. We have, therefore, studied the mechanism of its reaction with *p*-substituted anisoles in the presence of NaOAc and Hg(OAc)₂ in 50% aq. HOAc at 303 K. The role of Hg(OAc)₂ is to prevent any Br⁻ (and hence Br₂) being formed in the reaction mixture thus enabling NBSA alone to function as a brominating agent³.

Experimental

Liquid organic compounds (extra pure) were used after distillation. Solid organic compounds (extra pure) were used after checking their m.p.

NBSA solution was taken along with NaOAc and Hg(OAc)₂. The required quantity of *p*-substituted anisole was then added and mixed well. 5 ml aliquots of the reaction mixture (50 ml) at different intervals of time were pipetted out into KI solution to arrest the reaction. The liberated iodine was titrated against thiosulphate.

Results and Discussion

For NBSA bromination of *p*-nitroanisole (PNA) in the presence of NaOAc and Hg(OAc)₂ in 50% aq. HOAc, the order for NBSA is unity as shown by the linear plot of log[NBSA] vs t. The orders for PNA, NaOAc and Hg(OAc)₂ are fractional, i.e., 0.7 for PNA, 0.4 for NaOAc and 0.3 for Hg(OAc)₂. The values were obtained from the slopes of log k₁ vs log [PNA], log [NaOAc] or log [Hg(OAc)₂]. The k₁ for the bromination was found to decrease steadily on the addition of saccharin.

Mechanism A :

For PNA-NBSA reaction in the presence of NaOAc and Hg(OAc)₂ NBSA reacts in a fast equilibrium to produce BrOAc. This attacks the PNA to form a π -complex which decomposes in a slow step to form the product.

The above mechanism explains the fractional order for PNA.

Mechanism B :

With initially added saccharin, NBSA reacts with HOAc in a fast equilibrium step to form saccharin and BrOAc. BrOAc then attacks PNA in a slow

$$\text{Rate} = \frac{k_1 k_2 [\text{NBSA}] [\text{PNA}] [\text{NaOAc}]}{[\text{Na-Sacc}] [K_m + [\text{PNA}]]}$$

Mechanism in the presence of NaOAc and Hg(OAc)₂.

step and forms a σ -complex, which loses a proton in a fast step to produce the product.

Mechanism in presence of initially added saccharin.

Substituent effect :

To find out whether the reaction mechanism involves a carbocationic intermediate, we have investigated the NBSA bromination of PNA, *p*-chloroanisole (PCA), *p*-bromoanisole (PBA) and *p*-anisic acid (PAA), in the presence of initially added saccharin (to keep the rate low and readily measurable).

The plot of 1/(a-x) vs t for *p*-substituted anisoles were found to be linear showing thereby the total order is two.

The relative reactivities of the *p*-substituted anisoles are shown below.

NBS	1	208	381	422	1436
NBSA	1	24	16	25	

Relative reactivity of *p*-substituted anisoles.

Hammett equation :

A linear free-energy correlation was attempted by casting the data into an extended form of Hammett equation⁴.

$$\log k/k_0 = \rho \sum_1 \sigma_1$$

The σ_o value for methoxy and σ_m values of the various substituents ($-\text{NO}_2$, $-\text{CO}_2\text{H}$, $-\text{Br}$, $-\text{Cl}$) were taken from literature⁵ to calculate $\sum_1 \sigma_1$. From the slope of the Hammett plot of $\log k_2$ vs $\sum_1 \sigma_1$, ρ was found to be -7.63 .

Fig. 1. Hammett plot for NBSA bromination of *p*-substituted anisoles.

For NBS bromination of the above anisoles the ρ value was found⁶ to be -7.85 . The magnitude of ρ and its negative sign suggest that the above NBS and NBSA brominations proceed through a carbocationic intermediate.

To compare the relative reactivities of Br_2 , NBS and NBSA we have investigated the bromination of PNA by these reagents in 50% aq. HOAc at 303 K. NBS is only slightly more reactive than Br_2 but NBSA is 18 times more reactive than Br_2 (Table 1).

TABLE 1—RELATIVE REACTIVITIES OF BROMINATING AGENTS

Brominating Agent	$k_1 \times 10^6$ (sec ⁻¹)	Relative reactivity
Br_2	1.05	1.0
NBS	1.77	1.7
NBSA	19.1	18.2

[PNA] = 0.020 M; 50% aq. HOAc, 303 K;
[Br_2] = [NBS] = [NBSA] = 0.002 M.

Also, NBSA is a crystalline solid which is easier to handle than liquid Br_2 . Thus, there is a great potential for the use of NBSA as a brominating agent for aromatic compounds.

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Kinetics and Mechanism of Ce(IV) Oxidation of 4-Methyl Morpholine in Perchloric Acid Media

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RECENTLY, ceric perchlorate oxidation of some substrates in perchloric acid media has been reported¹⁻¹¹. In some cases the mechanistic approach has been based via free radical formation. Thus, mechanism suggested by various authors is not uniform and any inference made on analogy would be naive. The present study aims at getting more definite information regarding the mechanism of oxidation of 4-methyl morpholine by Ce(IV) in perchloric acid solutions.

Experimental

The sample of 4-methyl morpholine was E. Merck product. All other chemicals were of B.D.H., A.R. grade. The rate of oxidation was determined titrimetrically⁹.

Results and Discussion

The results obtained under different conditions are listed in Table 1. The constant value of pseudo first order rate constant shows that the reaction follows first order kinetics with respect to ceric

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